

RESULTS OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF OBESITY AGAINST THE BACKGROUND OF TYPE 2 DIABETES MELLITUS WITH TRADITIONAL TREATMENT

APPROACHES

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ABSTRACT

According to experts of the International Diabetes Federation, by 2045 the incidence will be 629 million people. Type 2 DM is complicated by renal failure in 40-55% of cases, cardiovascular system diseases in 50-60%, and often causes lower limb amputations [2]. To reduce body weight, it is necessary to change lifestyle, follow pharmacotherapy and, if indicated, bariatric surgery. In cases of significant obesity, patients are advised to consider bariatric surgery, which is one of the treatment methods offered to patients with type 2 diabetes [1].

Relevance of the problem. According to experts of the International Diabetes Federation, by 2045 the incidence will be 629 million people. Type 2 DM is complicated by renal failure in 40-55% of cases, cardiovascular system diseases in 50-60%, and often causes lower limb amputations [2]. To reduce body weight, it is necessary to change lifestyle, follow pharmacotherapy and, if indicated, bariatric surgery. In cases of significant obesity, patients are advised to consider bariatric surgery, which is one of the treatment methods offered to patients with type 2 diabetes [1].

Thus, modern literature data indicate that BOIs are an effective method for treating obesity and type 2 diabetes mellitus, however, they are accompanied by a risk of both early and late complications. In patients with type 2 diabetes, these complications often have a more pronounced course and require long-term multidisciplinary observation. Considering the problem of obesity, including MO against a background of type 2 diabetes mellitus, it is necessary to further consolidate efforts to develop unified, specific therapeutic and diagnostic algorithms for actions and a differentiated approach to performing bariatric surgical interventions, which is the reason for conducting this study.

The aim of the study is to improve the results of surgical treatment of obesity, including morbid obesity against the background of type 2 diabetes mellitus, by determining modifications in the methods and technical techniques of bariatric surgical interventions.

Research material and methods. The work is based on the results of a retrospective and prospective analysis of 159 patients with morbid obesity (MO) against the background of type

2 diabetes mellitus for the period from 2023 to 2024, who were subjected to surgical treatment at the "Sehat" private clinic in Andijan and the third surgical department of the Andijan State Medical Institute Clinic.

According to the goals and objectives of the study, it is conditionally divided into two groups:

- **comparison group** - (2023) - 57 (35.8%) patients, who underwent a retrospective analysis of the results of surgical treatment in compliance with traditional approaches;

- **main group** - (2024) - 102 (64.2%) patients, who underwent a prospective study of the results of surgical treatment using a differentiated approach to performing bariatric surgical interventions.

To achieve the goal and objectives of the study, general clinical, laboratory, biochemical, instrumental, and statistical research methods were used according to the protocols approved by the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Results and their discussion. The identified shortcomings of the traditional approach to surgical treatment of obesity against the background of type 2 diabetes served as a basis for revising the existing tactics and developing an improved treatment and diagnostic algorithm. In the main group of patients, a differentiated approach was implemented, expanding age-related indications for surgical treatment, optimizing the choice of bariatric intervention type, and implementing modified surgical techniques.

As clinical experience accumulated and the causes of "postbariatric complications" were analyzed in our team, GSH and PRJ surgery methods were modified, for which patents for invention IAP 7843 dated 24.09.2024 and IAP 20240549/1 dated 04.04.2025 were obtained.

It is important to note that with the accumulation of practical experience in performing bariatric surgical interventions in patients with varying degrees of obesity against the background of type 2 diabetes mellitus, as well as the analysis of immediate and long-term treatment results, there is a need for further optimization of the technical aspects of surgical interventions. One of the key elements influencing the effectiveness of the restrictive and metabolic components of bariatric interventions is the diameter of the esophageal-gastric calibration probe used.

In the previous stages of the work, the diameter of the calibrated esophageal-gastric tube did not differ depending on the degree of obesity, which in a number of cases could lead to insufficient restriction in patients with morbid obesity or, conversely, to excessive restriction in patients with less pronounced forms of obesity. In this regard, to increase the effectiveness of surgical treatment and reduce the frequency of functional and metabolic complications, we have developed and implemented a modified method for using an esophageal-gastric calibration probe depending on the degree of obesity.

According to the proposed algorithm: in the first degree of obesity against the background of type 2 diabetes mellitus, the use of a 40 Fr diameter esophageal-gastric calibration probe is justified; in the second degree of obesity, the use of a 38 Fr diameter calibration probe; in the third degree of obesity (morbid obesity), the use of a 36 Fr diameter calibration probe. A differentiated approach to selecting the calibration probe diameter made it possible to more accurately adapt the volume of the formed gastric reservoir and the degree of restriction to the patient's initial anthropometric and metabolic characteristics.

The justification for the proposed modification is based on the fact that patients with varying degrees of obesity differ significantly in: stomach volume and its adaptive capabilities; severity of hyperphagia and eating disorders; degree of insulin resistance and hormonal-metabolic disorders; risk of functional complications (vomiting, reflux, stenosis, dumping syndrome).

The use of a wider calibration probe (40 Fr) in patients with the first degree of obesity allows avoiding excessive restriction, reduces the risk of postoperative dysphagia, gastroesophageal reflux, and nutritional disorders, while maintaining a sufficient metabolic effect.

Conversely, in patients with second and especially third-degree obesity, reducing the calibration probe diameter to 38 Fr and 36 Fr provides adequate restriction, contributes to more pronounced and persistent weight loss, and potentiates the metabolic effect of the operation, including improvement of carbohydrate metabolism and type 2 diabetes compensation.

Conclusion. Thus, the developed and implemented modified method of differentiated use of the esophageal-gastric calibration probe depending on the degree of obesity made it possible to increase the effectiveness and safety of bariatric surgical interventions in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus with obesity.

Individualization of the calibration probe diameter ensures the optimal level of restriction, reduces the risk of functional complications, and promotes more stable correction of metabolic disorders. In combination with other modifications of surgical tactics, this approach is an important element in optimizing surgical treatment and improving its immediate and long-term results.

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